

D4.1: Existing climate data

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WP 4, T 4.1

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List of abbreviations

CCS Core Case Studies
 CDS Climate Data Store
 CLC CORINE Land Cover
 CMIP Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase
 C3S Copernicus Climate Change Service
 ECMWF European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
 ERA European Reanalyses
 EU European Union
 FAR First Assessment Report
 GCM Global Climate Model
 GHGs GreenHouse Gases
 IPCC Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
 JRC Joint Research Centre
 MMU Minimum Mapping Unit
 RCP Representative Concentration Pathway
 SAR Second Assessment Report
 SFTP Secure File Transfer Protocol
 SSP Shared Socioeconomic Pathway
 SST Sea Surface Temperature
 TAR Third Assessment Report
 WCRP World Climate Research Programme

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the climate data used by climate modelling partners to produce local climate scenarios for the DISTENDER core case studies (CCS). The local climate data will be used to drive WP5 impact models and to produce climate indicators for the T5.7 Risk and vulnerability assessment. For each of the four global climate scenarios, projections will be calculated using statistical and dynamical downscaling techniques. This deliverable is the outcome of the T4.1 “Acquisition and analysis of existing simulations and observations” with the objective: “Collect and store the data required by the models and tools of the WPs and which are not the responsibility of the case studies (defined in task T9.2.1), e.g., outputs of the global climate models. Data will be analysed to better understanding and managing climate risks in climate-sensitive sectors”.

The four global climate scenarios that have been selected in DISTENDER are the corresponding Tier 1 CMIP6 scenarios: SSP126, SSP245, SSP370, SSP585. Outputs from global climate models for these four scenarios are available through the CMIP6 search interface under the auspices of the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP). Daily and monthly global climate projections data from CMIP6 are available through Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) which is the main user interface of the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) implemented by ECMWF on behalf of the EU. Due to the large size of these dataset, the global climate data will not be uploaded in the DISTENDER SFTP. These data will be available locally and can be uploaded into the SFTP as specific request from other partners.

Simulations have been generated by multiple independent climate research centres in an effort coordinated by the WCRP and assessed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). These climate projections underpin the conclusions of the IPCC Assessment Reports that “Continued emission of greenhouse gases will cause further warming and long-lasting changes in all components of the climate system, increasing the likelihood of severe, pervasive and irreversible impacts for people and ecosystems”.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The global climate is undergoing significant changes and is expected to continue to do so in the coming decades and beyond. The extent of this change will depend on the amount of greenhouse gases (heat-trapping) that are released into the atmosphere, as well as the level of uncertainty surrounding the Earth's sensitivity to these emissions. If greenhouse gases (GHGs) emissions are substantially reduced, the rise in the global average temperature could be limited to 2°C or less. However, if emissions continue at current levels, the temperature could rise by 5°C or more by the end of the century, compared to preindustrial levels. Human activities are the primary cause of the rapid pace of climate change, which is now faster than any other point in the known history of the Earth's climate. Scientific evidence indicates that unmitigated carbon emissions will cause global warming of at least several degrees Celsius by 2100, resulting in significant risks to human society and natural ecosystems at the local, regional, and global levels. The impacts of global climate change have already been felt across all regions of the planet and many economic sectors (Climate Change Knowledge Portal, 2023).

Throughout the 20th century, various changes have been observed in the climate system, which includes a rise in global air and ocean temperature, an increase in global sea levels, and a persistent and widespread reduction of snow and ice cover. Additionally, there have been alterations in atmospheric and ocean circulation, along with regional weather patterns that have affected seasonal rainfall conditions. The primary reason for these changes is due to the extra heat present in the climate system caused by the addition of GHGs to the atmosphere. Human activities such as the burning of fossil fuels (coal, oil, and natural gas), deforestation, agriculture, and land-use changes have contributed to the increase in GHGs, which have a heat-trapping effect on the atmosphere. The observed changes in the climate system align with an increased greenhouse effect, and other natural factors like volcanoes, the sun, and natural variability cannot fully explain the scale and timing of these changes (Climate Change Knowledge Portal, 2023).

1.1 Climate scenarios

A climate scenario is a plausible image of a future climate based on knowledge of the past climate and assumptions on future change on increase of GHG concentrations.

Typically, global climate models (GCMs) are utilized to construct these scenarios, which simulate climate change by gradually augmenting atmospheric GHG concentrations. This involves making decisions about how GHG concentrations will change in the future, which are then converted into scenarios and incorporated into the GCM (CoastAdapt, 2023). While the climate of the future will continue to undergo natural variability similar to that of the past, the underlying changes in mean climate will persist, driven by human activities at a pace largely determined by current and future GHG and aerosol emissions. As future emissions remain uncertain, it is often recommended for many applications to utilize a range of plausible scenarios representing high to low emission pathways.

The scenarios used in climate modelling are a combination of socioeconomic and climate forcing (i.e., radiative forcing) “pathways”. The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) describe how global societies might evolve with respect to population

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growth, inequality within and across countries, socioeconomic developments, energy use, technology changes, and environmental conditions. Each SSP is translated into future projections of energy, land use/cover change, and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, which are inputs to climate models. Radiative forcing is essentially the change in the difference between incoming solar radiation from the sun, and outgoing energy radiated back into space by Earth. By convention, a positive radiative forcing means more energy is retained within the climate system, leading to climate warming, whereas a negative radiative forcing means more energy is leaving the system than is retained, leading to climate cooling.

1.1.1 Description of existing future scenarios

The practice of utilizing scenarios to forecast climate changes in the future originated with the IPCC scenarios, designated as Scenarios A through D, which were introduced in the IPCC's First Assessment Report (FAR) in 1990. These scenarios calculated emissions between 1990 and 2100 and the corresponding atmospheric concentrations of carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and trichlorofluoromethane (CFC-11). The IPCC scenarios were subsequently replaced by the first official set of scenarios, the IS92 scenarios, implemented in the IPCC's Second Assessment Report (SAR) in 1996. The IS92 scenarios were the first to estimate future concentrations for the complete range of greenhouse gases (GHGs) over the period from 1990 to 2100. These scenarios were employed in relatively straightforward climate models to generate predictions of future climate change. Under the World Climate Research Program (WCRP), the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) facilitates climate model simulations globally. CMIP strives to advance comprehension and forecasting of climate change in the past, present, and future through a multi-model approach. To enable comparisons of model outcomes, CMIP is establishing criteria for simulations, data structures, and assessment algorithms, among other measures. These efforts will provide climate scientists data to directly exchange, contrast, and assess their research (DKRZ, 2023).

The first improvement to the original IS92 scenarios were the Special Report on Emissions Scenarios (SRES) scenarios, used for the First (1996) and Second Phases (1997) of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP1 & CMIP2) and IPCC's Third Assessment Report (TAR) (2001), as well as the Third Phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP3) (2005-2007) and the IPCC's Fourth Assessment Report (AR4) (2007). Scientists and experts from a broad range of backgrounds and specialties developed six SRES scenario families which covered a wide range of potential climate drivers including demographic, technological, and economic developments.

The SRES scenarios were replaced by Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) for the Fifth Phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5) (2008-2013) and IPCC Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) (2014) (CMIP4 was skipped to align CMIP and IPCC AR numbering). RCPs describe the concentration of GHGs in the atmosphere over time and are labelled according to the Earth's simulated total radiative forcing in 2100. RCPs are plausible scenarios for humanity's emissions of GHGs based on plausible future developments but have no specified associated socio-economic conditions. The latest iteration of scenarios, used for CMIP6 (2016-2021) and IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) (2021), are the Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs).

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The SRES scenarios were replaced by the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) for the Fifth Phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5) (2008-2013) and IPCC Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) (2014), with the intention of aligning the numbering of CMIP and IPCC AR. RCPs define the concentration of greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere over time and are categorized by the simulated total radiative forcing of Earth in 2100. RCPs provide feasible scenarios for the emission of GHGs by human activity, based on realistic future developments, but do not specify associated socio-economic conditions. The latest generation of scenarios, employed for CMIP6 (2016-2021) and IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) (2021), are known as the Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs).

Multi-model climate projections are a crucial source of information for decision-making related to mitigation and adaptation. The experimental design of the Scenario Model Intercomparison Project (ScenarioMIP) for the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project phase 6 (CMIP6) is described by O'Neill et al. (2016) in detail, including the origin and rationale. The experiments generate projections for 21st century scenarios based on the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) developed by integrated assessment models (IAMs) to create anthropogenic emissions and land-use scenarios consistent with the qualitative narratives and quantitative elements of each SSP. Baseline scenarios were produced that assumed no explicit mitigation policies beyond those in place at the time the scenarios were created, prior to the Paris Agreement. Additionally, emissions and land-use scenarios were produced that included mitigation policies to achieve a range of radiative forcing targets for the end of the century. Given a particular SSP, multiple levels of radiative forcings are achievable based on more or less stringent mitigation. The ScenarioMIP design selected a subset of scenarios to be run by global climate and Earth system models (ESMs) in concentration-driven mode. Some of these scenarios were chosen specifically to provide continuity with the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), including SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, SSP4-6.0, and SSP5-8.5, where the numbers represent the stratospheric-adjusted radiative forcing in Wm^{-2} by the end of the 21st century as estimated by the IAMs (Tebaldi et al., 2021). The following narratives were developed to describe the underlying global conditions in each SSP, see Table 1. These descriptions were taken directly from Riahi et. al (2017).

Table 1. Summary of the description of the SSPs.

Scenarios	Narrative
SSP1	<p>Sustainability – Taking the Green Road (Low challenges to mitigation and adaptation)</p> <p>The world shifts gradually, but pervasively, toward a more sustainable path, emphasizing more inclusive development that respects perceived environmental boundaries. Management of the global commons slowly improves, educational and health investments accelerate the demographic transition, and the emphasis on economic growth shifts toward a broader emphasis on human well-being. Driven by an increasing commitment to achieving development goals, inequality is reduced both across and within countries. Consumption is oriented toward low material growth and lower resource and energy intensity.</p>
SSP2	<p>Middle of the Road (Medium challenges to mitigation and adaptation)</p>

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	<p>The world follows a path in which social, economic, and technological trends do not shift markedly from historical patterns. Development and income growth proceeds unevenly, with some countries making relatively good progress while others fall short of expectations. Global and national institutions work toward but make slow progress in achieving sustainable development goals. Environmental systems experience degradation, although there are some improvements and overall, the intensity of resource and energy use declines. Global population growth is moderate and levels off in the second half of the century. Income inequality persists or improves only slowly and challenges to reducing vulnerability to societal and environmental changes remain.</p>
SSP3	<p>Regional Rivalry – A Rocky Road (High challenges to mitigation and adaptation)</p> <p>A resurgent nationalism, concerns about competitiveness and security, and regional conflicts push countries to increasingly focus on domestic or, at most, regional issues. Policies shift over time to become increasingly oriented toward national and regional security issues. Countries focus on achieving energy and food security goals within their own regions at the expense of broader-based development. Investments in education and technological development decline. Economic development is slow, consumption is material-intensive, and inequalities persist or worsen over time. Population growth is low in industrialized and high in developing countries. A low international priority for addressing environmental concerns leads to strong environmental degradation in some regions.</p>
SSP4	<p>Inequality – A Road Divided (Low challenges to mitigation, high challenges to adaptation)</p> <p>Highly unequal investments in human capital, combined with increasing disparities in economic opportunity and political power, lead to increasing inequalities and stratification both across and within countries. Over time, a gap widens between an internationally connected society that contributes to knowledge and capital intensive sectors of the global economy, and a fragmented collection of lower-income, poorly educated societies that work in a labor intensive, low-tech economy. Social cohesion degrades and conflict and unrest become increasingly common. Technology development is high in the high-tech economy and sectors. The globally connected energy sector diversifies, with investments in both carbon-intensive fuels like coal and unconventional oil, but also low-carbon energy sources. Environmental policies focus on local issues around middle and high income areas.</p>
SSP5	<p>Fossil-fueled Development – Taking the Highway (High challenges to mitigation, low challenges to adaptation)</p> <p>This world places increasing faith in competitive markets, innovation, and participatory societies to produce rapid technological progress and development of human capital as the path to sustainable development. Global markets are increasingly integrated. There are also strong investments in health, education, and institutions to enhance human and social capital. At the same time, the push for economic and social development is coupled with the</p>

exploitation of abundant fossil fuel resources and the adoption of resource and energy intensive lifestyles around the world. All these factors lead to rapid growth of the global economy, while global population peaks and declines in the 21st century. Local environmental problems like air pollution are successfully managed. There is faith in the ability to effectively manage social and ecological systems, including by geo-engineering if necessary.

Each SSP generates a corresponding projection of greenhouse gas emissions and land-use change under the corresponding SSP baseline scenario. These SSPs are designed to be used in conjunction with a new and improved version of Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), which allows for the incorporation of different climate policy futures, such as the adoption of renewable energy over fossil fuels, and the ease or difficulty of reaching the end-of-century radiative forcing goal specified by an RCP. The different policy scenarios result in different levels of radiative forcing, which is a measure of the extent to which greenhouse gases in the atmosphere warm or cool the climate, expressed in watts per square meter (W/m^2) by the year 2100. These values range from 1.9 to $8.5 W/m^2$, with higher values indicating stronger climate warming effects. The selected forcing values were chosen to allow for easy comparison of the new scenarios to the RCPs used in the CMIP5 and IPCC AR5. Not all possible combinations of SSPs and forcing scenarios are feasible, and therefore, some do not have simulations. For instance, SSP5, which prioritizes fossil-fuel development and results in high emissions, is incompatible with a low forcing scenario (e.g., $1.9 W/m^2$), which would necessitate stricter climate policy and strong mitigation, and hence, low greenhouse gas emissions (Government of Canada, 2023).

Possible combinations of SSPs with the corresponding RCPs are shown in Figure 1. The high number of possible scenarios, shown as boxes of any colour, led ScenarioMIP to designate levels of priority to certain scenarios for modelling organizations. Four scenarios were designated as 'Tier 1' (blue) scenarios and considered the top priority in the ScenarioMIP experimental design, these are the selected scenarios in DISTENDER. These Tier 1 scenarios span a broad range of uncertainty in future socio-economic and climate forcing pathways and serve as good comparisons to RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP6.0, and RCP8.5 scenarios used for CMIP5. The 'Tier 2' (yellow) scenarios include additional scenarios of interest for modelling centres to explore if resources allowed. The denomination of individual scenarios comprises the name of the basic pathway followed by two numerals indicating the additional radiative forcing achieved by the year 2100 in units of tenths of watts (DKRZ, 2023b).

Figure 1 depicts the possible combinations of SSPs with their corresponding RCP, which are represented as boxes of different colours. Due to the large number of scenarios, the Scenario Model Intercomparison Project (ScenarioMIP) assigned priority levels to certain scenarios for modeling organizations. Four scenarios were designated as 'Tier 1' (blue) and considered the highest priority, including the selected scenarios in DISTENDER. These Tier 1 scenarios span a broad range of uncertainty in future socio-economic and climate forcing pathways and are good comparisons to the RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP6.0, and RCP8.5 scenarios used for CMIP5. The 'Tier 2' (yellow) scenarios include additional scenarios of interest for modeling centers to explore if resources allow. Individual scenarios are named after the basic pathway followed by two numerals indicating the additional radiative forcing achieved by the year 2100 in tenths of watts, as per the DKRZ (2023b).

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Figure 1. Shared Socio-economic Pathways and year 2100 radiative forcing combinations used in ScenarioMIP. (Source: O'Neill et al. 2016)

The DISTENDER global climate scenarios (Tier 1 of CMIP6, O'Neill et al. 2016) are:

- **SSP585:** With an additional radiative forcing of 8.5 W/m² by the year 2100, this scenario represents the upper boundary of the range of scenarios described in the literature. It can be understood as an update of the CMIP5 scenario RCP8.5, now combined with socioeconomic reasons.
- **SSP370:** With 7 W/m² by the year 2100, this scenario is in the upper-middle part of the full range of scenarios. It was newly introduced after the RCP scenarios, closing the gap between RCP6.0 and RCP8.5.
- **SSP245:** As an update to scenario RCP4.5, SSP245 with an additional radiative forcing of 4.5 W/m² by the year 2100 represents the medium pathway of future greenhouse gas emissions. This scenario assumes that climate protection measures are being taken.
- **SSP126:** This scenario with 2.6 W/m² by the year 2100 is a remake of the optimistic scenario RCP2.6 and was designed with the aim of simulating a development that is compatible with the 2°C target. This scenario, too, assumes climate protection measures being taken.

In the Figure 2 can see the temporal evolution of the radiative forcing.

Figure 2. Anthropogenic radiative forcing (W/m^2) of resulting from the selected scenarios in DISTENDER. (Source: O'Neill et al. 2016).

1.1.2 Uncertainty in Future Projections

The future climate change is uncertain due to various factors such as natural variability, human choices, and scientific uncertainty, which includes uncertainty in scientific modeling and climate sensitivity. Scientific uncertainty has two components: parametric uncertainty, which occurs when GCMs are unable to simulate processes that occur on smaller spatial or temporal scales than they can resolve, and structural uncertainty, which arises when GCMs cannot accurately represent all important physical processes occurring on scales they can resolve. This could be because a process is not yet known or not understood well enough to be modeled accurately. In the near future, the majority of the range of uncertainty in projected global and regional change will be due to natural variability and scientific limitations in our ability to model and understand the Earth's climate system. However, by about 2030, human choices will become increasingly important in determining the magnitude and patterns of future global warming. Despite the continued occurrence of natural variability, most of the difference between present and future climates will be determined by the decisions society makes today and over the next few decades. As we look further into the future, the influence of human choices on the magnitude of future warming will increase (Science Global Change, 2023).

1.2 Global climate models and downscaling

Models are fundamental tools for studying the potential impacts of climate change, including changes in temperature, precipitation, and sea level. We can define a climate model: ***“mathematical model for quantitatively describing, simulating, and analyzing the***

interactions between the Earth-ocean-atmosphere system using the fundamental thermodynamic equations to describe the behaviour of the system". GCMs divide the earth into many layers and thousands of three-dimensional gridded spaces. These models are skilled at replicating past and current climate. For example, GCMs accurately reproduce observed temporal warming trends, sea ice dynamics, and extreme weather events (Schramm, 2020).

The configuration of a GCM is shown in Figure 3. These models have a three-dimensional grid and, when the model is being run, the model values (energy, pressure etc.) are calculated at the grid intersections for each time step (typically, 20 minutes). The resolution of the grid is one determinant of how long a typical 100-year model run will take. Run lengths are typically of the order of weeks to months. In order to use a GCM to study climate change, modellers will increase the concentrations of GHGs in the model atmosphere and observe the effect (CoastAdpat, 2023).

Figure 3: Typical structure of a General Circulation Model. Source: NOAA 2012

The climate projections for potential future shifts are determined by various scenarios using climate models. These models are simulated multiple times under different conditions, including population levels and estimated emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other GHGs. Each GCM has unique characteristics and sensitivity to emissions of GHGs. The range of GCMs is essential to scientists for understanding the uncertainty associated with future events based on a particular scenario and time frame. To account for this range and use the full scope of projections, ensembles of multiple GCM simulations are often utilized (Schramm, 2020).

GCMs have been extensively utilized to construct future climate scenarios, but their outputs are often too coarse to be utilized in impact models that require higher spatial and temporal resolutions of the projections. Such high-resolution climate scenarios are critical for climate

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change impact evaluation and adaptation at regional and local levels because decision-makers and local stakeholders must first understand what the anticipated climate will be like before taking any mitigation and adaptation actions (Guo et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2022). There are two main methods for obtaining regional detail from the coarse resolution of GCM:

- The **statistical downscaling** methods generally involve two main steps. The first step is the development of statistical relationships between local climate variables (e.g., surface air temperature and precipitation) and largescale predictors. The next step is the application of such relationships to the output of GCM experiments in order to simulate local climate characteristics, with the assumption that these statistical relationships remain the same in the future. The statistical methods have an advantage in requiring less expensive computation than the high-resolution dynamic model-based approach, which allows quick application to multiple GCMs. However, they have a major disadvantage in that they do not represent physical processes, and the internal relationships are kept fixed in the future. In addition, developing a statistical downscaling method will always require rather extensive observational data.
- Numerical dynamic models (**dynamical downscaling**) at high resolution over the region of interest can be used to obtain high resolution climate scenarios. These high-resolution dynamic models are based on the same systems of physical equations used in GCMs and are considered to best capture the complex atmospheric process. The high resolutions enable the model to represent some weather extremes and orographic effect precipitation. Like coarse-scale GCMs, this method requires heavy computation which limits the number of scenarios that can be performed. CM is also dependent on GCM as the boundary conditions. Through higher resolution, however, RCM can better represent important physical processes than the statistical method and can improve the physical realism of simulated regional circulation.

These regional phenomena play a significant role in the occurrence of natural hazards and their impacts. Therefore, future climate projections must take into account the regional peculiarities to understand climate-related risk more reliably. Further, to provide adequate local scale climate information, it is necessary to apply some downscaling process based on statistical or dynamical approaches (Ribalaygua et al. 2013, Monjo et al. 2016). For instance, dynamical downscaling of CMIP6 is currently running (Euro-CORDEX 2022), while statistical downscaling efforts were recently performed in the Chelsa project (Brun et al. 2022) and Copernicus-C3S (2020, 2022). The data collected in T4.1 need further downscaling to local scales. This task researches the best approach to provide past and future localized climate information, considering dynamical downscaling, statistical/empirical advancement and bias corrections. Detailed information about the downscaling techniques will be found in D4.2 “D4.2 Downscaling techniques”.

1.3 Links with other DISTENDER tasks

The task T4.1 is inside of the data-collection related methods (WP4 and WP9) and modelling tasks (WP4, WP5 and WP7). WP4 “Downscaling climate scenarios” will produce input data to the WP5 “Risk & Vulnerability assessment” models. The objective of WP4 is the production of local climate scenarios for the CCS based on techniques developed in former

projects. A flexible combination of dynamical and statistical downscaling methods will be optimized and applied in the project's test cases and the starting point is the T4.1 "Acquisition and analysis of existing simulations and observations". The data will be downscaled using the techniques describe in the T4.2 "Downscaling techniques" to produce the local climate scenarios of the T4.3.

The task T4.1 has been developed in parallel with task T9.2 "Data requirements" which is also led by UPM. Both tasks aim to ensure that the modelers of WP4, WP5 and WP7 have the necessary data to perform their modelling tasks in DISTENDER. There are five DISTENDER core case studies (CCS): CS 01 Austria; CS 02 the NE of the Netherlands; CS 03 Dehesa and Montado (Spain and Portugal); CS 04 Guimarães (Portugal); CS 05 Metropolitan City of Turin (Italy). Detailed information about each case study can be found in D9.1 "Case studies". It contains information reported by the case studies on potential climate hazards, impacts or negative influences, that will provide the insights for the impact models which are central to WP5 Risk and Vulnerability Assessment addressing health (GHG emissions, urban heat, air quality), water, energy and agriculture. Model domains are also presented for each case study which cover the areas of simulation for all the mentioned models in each case study.

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2 OBSERVATIONAL DATA

2.1 ECMWF ERA5 Datasets

To validate downscaling techniques, it is necessary to use a reference reanalysis of the past climate. The European reanalyses named ERA5 (atmospheric) and ERA5-Land (surface) are selected to be used in the task T4.2, for several reasons: 1) they are developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), whose main geographical area of work is where DISTENDER takes place, and whose weather forecasts are proved to be among the best available; 2) They are the most current versions of the European reanalysis which entails an improvement in spatial and temporal resolution with respect to the previous ones; and 3) their download is free of charge through the Copernicus program (Climate Change Service: DOI: 10.24381/cds.adbb2d47). The ERA5/ERA5-Land were released in 2019 and their temporal coverage is still being expanded. ERA5-Land is the version for surface variables, and it only covers land terrain, but worldwide with fine resolution, providing data for up to 50 different variables.

The first approach to define a European grid for DISTENDER is based on the ERA5-Land framework, which provides 196367 inland points. ERA5-Land's coverage is a global grid with a spatial resolution of $0.073^\circ \times 0.073^\circ$ (approx. 8km x 8km). Its vertical coverage ranges from 2 metres above the surface level to a soil depth of 289 cm and 4 levels of the ECMWF surface model: Layer 1: 0-7cm, Layer 2: 7-28cm, Layer 3: 28-100cm, Layer 4: 100-289cm. Some parameters are defined at 2 m over the surface. ERA5-Land gives hourly data from January 1981 to present (data are updated monthly with a delay of about three months relative to the actual date).

From all the variables available to download, only some of them were firstly identified to be used; mostly those related to the usual atmospheric observations needed from weather stations: 2m Air Temperature, Humidity, Total Precipitation, U Component of the Wind, V Component of the Wind (Table 2).

Table 2. Variables and their main characteristics selected from ECMWF ERA5-Land.

Variable	Daily scale	Comments
Hourly temperature	-Maximum temperature -Minimum temperature -Mean temperature	Hourly temperature values allow to obtain with great detail not only maximum and minimum daily temperature but also to obtain mean daily temperature with more significance than when obtained only with max and min values.
Hourly dew point temperature	-Maximum specific temperature -Maximum relative humidity -Maximum Heat Index	Dew point Temperature is a variable that points at which temperature value the atmosphere would reach saturation and its moisture would start condensing in droplets. Therefore, it is an indicator of the net content of moisture of the atmosphere, being useful to get the Specific Humidity (q); moreover, the closer this value is to the actual temperature, the higher that Relative Humidity (RH) will be. Thus, Dew point Temperature at this hourly scale gives great information about the moisture content

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		of the atmosphere in each hour of the day, and allow, by crossing these values with those hourly and daily values of temperature previously obtained, to obtain several derived variables, such as: Maximum q, maximum HR or Heat Index.
Hourly precipitation	24-h accumulation of precipitation	Precipitation hourly values have been aggregated at daily intervals to obtain the 24-h accumulation of precipitation for each day. Daily values are afterward treated to obtain at monthly scale, both monthly total precipitation for each point and the maximum precipitation accumulated at 24h for each month. Precipitation units are adapted from “m” to “mm” for a more intuitive use.
Hourly wind speed (U and V components)	Maximum daily mean wind speed	In the case of wind, ERA5-Land available hourly data corresponds to both U and V wind components with the hourly mean values. Both components have been composed at hourly intervals according to the following rule: Wind Speed $=\sqrt{(U^2 + V^2)}$ since U and V are vectorial components of the wind module. With this procedure, we have obtained the mean hourly wind, which allows us to calculate its maximum values for each day and month.
Solar radiation	Solar radiation	Total solar radiation of ERA5-Land

The ERA5 is the last atmospheric reanalysis released from the ECMWF. Available since July 2019, it is the most accurate reanalysis available so far. It works with a huge set of data and observations from weather stations, soundings, satellites and other different reanalysis (like oceanic) as input at different atmospheric and sea levels. This way, ERA5 tries to reproduce with the most accuracy the real values that defined the atmospheric situation at a given time of the past. Due to its requirements of high-quality input, only data after satellite release is available.

ERA5 covers all of Europe’s land territory with a regular spatial resolution of 0.25° (30 km approx.). The monthly available variables are precipitation, mean temperature, runoff (total, surface, and sub-surface), and SST for the period 1979 to present.

The files are available in NetCDF format (ERA5_variable_monthlyEU.nc), with one file for each variable since the monthly basis resolution allows incorporating the whole-time coverage in it. As long as ERA5 data is available, we strongly encourage its use over CRU data, in addition to being the only source of Runoff available (see more information regarding the dataset in <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>).

ERA5 data were uploaded in the DISTENDER SFTP server for validation and calibration of impact models in WP5.

2.2 Meteorological observations from CCSs

The collection of observed meteorological data for each core case study has been done within the task T9.2 "Data requirements" and will be documented in depth in D9.2 "Data for case studies". Table 3 is a synthesis of the meteorological data available in each CCS. All data have been uploaded to the DISTENDER SFTP server.

Table 3. Summary of the available observational meteorological dataset in each CCSs.

CCSs	Variables	Measuring stations	Period
<i>Austria</i>	Wind speed Precipitation Temperature Pressure	260	1950 - 2022
<i>NE of the Netherlands</i>	Humidity Precipitation Pressure Shortwave radiation Temperature Wind	8	1950-2020
<i>Dehesa and Montado</i>	Precipitation Temperature Relative humidity Wind Evapotranspiration Radiation Solar radiation	38	1980-2022
<i>Guimaraes</i>	Pressure Temperature Humidity Wind Precipitation	4	1980-2020
<i>Metropolitan City of Turin</i>	Precipitation Temperature Humidity Wind	89	1990-2022

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2.3 Land use data

Land cover maps represent spatial information on different types (classes) of physical coverage of the Earth's surface, e.g., forests, grasslands, croplands, lakes, wetlands. Dynamic land cover maps include transitions of land cover classes over time and hence capture land cover changes. Land use maps contain spatial information on the arrangements, activities and inputs people undertake in a certain land cover type to produce, change, or maintain it. The land uses and covers of Europe are the most systematically mapped in the world today, and their associated datasets offer the greatest spatial and thematic detail. Thanks to the work done within the **Copernicus Land Monitoring programme** run by the European Environmental Agency (EEA) and the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission, there are many general LUC datasets covering most of the European continent. These general datasets map all land uses and covers on the ground, without focusing on any specific type. However, whereas some cover the whole of Europe, others only map specific local areas of interest, such as urban or coastal areas, riparian zones or spaces protected under the Nature 2000 network. CORINE Land Cover (CLC) is the flagship European LUC mapping programme and a reference worldwide.

DISTENDER has setup CORINE Land Cover (CLC) inventory as a reference land use data for the modelling tasks. CLC was initiated in 1985 (reference year 1990). Updates have been produced in 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018 (used as “actual state in DISTENDER”). It consists of an inventory of land cover in 44 classes. CLC uses a Minimum Mapping Unit (MMU) of 25 hectares (ha) for areal phenomena and a minimum width of 100 m for linear phenomena. The time series are complemented by change layers, which highlight changes in land cover with an MMU of 5 ha. Different MMUs mean that the change layer has higher resolution than the status layer. Due to differences in MMUs the difference between two status layers will not equal to the corresponding CLC-Changes layer. If you are interested in CLC-Changes between two neighbour surveys always use the CLC-Change layer.

The Eionet network National Reference Centres Land Cover (NRC/LC) is producing the national CLC databases, which are coordinated and integrated by EEA. CLC is produced by the majority of countries by visual interpretation of high-resolution satellite imagery. In a few countries semi-automatic solutions are applied, using national in-situ data, satellite image processing, GIS integration and generalisation. The 2012 version of CLC was the first one embedding the CLC time series in the Copernicus programme, thus ensuring sustainable funding for the future. The 2018 version also funded by Copernicus was produced in less than 1 year.

2.3.1 CLC 2018

The fifth CLC inventory for the reference year 2018 was produced under the Copernicus programme. There are three levels (level 2 is the most adequate for DISTENDER proposes), show in the Figure 4.

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Figure 4. CLC 2018 one-two-three levels classification. (Source: CLC 2018, Copernicus)

It has the shortest production time in the history of CLC inventories. All EEA39 countries were mapped. Data were published in February 2020. Main features of CLC2018:

- Multitemporal Sentinel-2 (and optionally Landsat-8) satellite images were provided to the national teams.
- In majority of countries visual photointerpretation (CAPI) following uniform methodology
- (AD03) was applied. The number of countries applying semi-automated or bottom-up methodology increased (eight in total), as Portugal was added to the former list including Finland, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, Norway, Spain, and Sweden.

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- 'Change mapping first' approach used (see details in Ch. VI. Mapping CLC Changes).
- Most of the QC was conducted in remote verifications. Italy and Spain were verified by regions.
- In producing the European products, a simplified border matching was applied.
- The coverage of CLC increased with Faroe Islands (autonomous territory within the Kingdom of Denmark)

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3 MODEL CLIMATE DATA

3.1 CMIP6

In 1996, the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) initiated a project to assess and compare global coupled climate model experiments, popularly known as Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP). The project has completed five phases until 2014, with tremendous success in providing multi-model output to climate researchers and users internationally. It has thus turned out to be a cornerstone of global climate change evaluations.

The successor phase six (CMIP6) of the project began in 2016 to sustain the progress made in understanding climate change and associated evolution with updated climate models. CMIP6 is visioned to support WCRP grand science challenges by focusing on three key scientific questions: 1) What is the earth system's response to forcing? 2) What are the sources of systematic climate model biases and their impact? 3) How can future changes in the earth's climate be assessed involving intricate internal variability and predictability?

These objectives are elaborated through 21 sub-projects known as MIPs, for example, aerosol chemistry, carbon cycles, radiative forcing, volcanic eruptions, ocean, land surface, ice sheets, monsoons, paleoclimate, geoengineering, and so forth. CMIP6 was planned initially to incorporate runs from 100 climate models generated at 49 modelling groups, and as of 2020, results from nearly 40 models have been published, highlighting significant improvements over phase five models. The historical simulations are available for 1850-2014, whereas future projections are from 2015 onwards. However, Climate scientists can use a few initial years of projection simulations for present-day climate assessment where historical runs are closely connected to future projections (Eyring et al., 2016).

The future projections are based on the new shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs) framework given by the energy modelling community in contribution to IPCC AR6. In the new framework, an integrated approach is attempted to produce scenarios from the combination of existing representative concentration pathways for climate projections, socioeconomic considerations, and climate policies. CMIP6 selects a number of SSPs for climate model run distributed among two tiers. Tier 1 includes SSP5-8.5, SSP3-7.0, SSP2-4.5, and SSP1-2.6. And SSP4-6.0, SSP4-3.4, SSP5-3.4, and SSP1-1.9 are considered in tier 2. (O' Neil 2016). More information was explained in section 1.1.

The climate sensitivity (measured as long-term warming after atmospheric CO₂ concentrations double) of CMIP6 models is higher than the phase five models. **The Canadian Earth System Model 5 (canESM5) is a highly sensitive climate model, and Max Plank Institute Earth System Model (MPI-ESM) is among the lowest (Table 2). The climate data from different CMIP6 models is collected and archived at Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) data replication centers.**

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Table 4. Information about the three CMIP6 climate models selected for DISTENDER.

CMIP6 Models	Climate Change level	Resolution	Responsible Centre	References
CanESM5	Upper (75%)	2,812° x 2,790°	Canadian Centre for Climate Modelling and Analysis (CC-CMA), Canada.	Swart, N.C. et al. (2019)
EC-EARTH3	Medium (50%)	0,703° x 0,702°	EC-EARTH Consortium	EC-Earth Consortium. (2019)
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	Lower (25%)	0,938° x 0,935°	Max-Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M), Germany.	Von Storch, J. et al. (2017)

3.2 CanESM5

The CanESM5 is an earth system model developed by Swart et al. (2019) to simulate historical and future climate change as well as short- and long-term variability, including decadal predictions. According to Swart et al. (2019), CanESM5 has a notably higher equilibrium climate sensitivity (5.6 K) than its predecessor, CanESM2 (3.7 K). The three-dimensional scheme consists of a general circulation model of the atmosphere (T63 spectral resolution approximately of 2.8°) and the ocean (nominally 1°), a land cover model, a sea-ice scheme, and an explicit land/ocean carbon cycle model. The model features relatively coarse resolution and high throughput, which facilitates the production of large ensembles. Regarding the CanESM5 components, the atmosphere is represented by the Canadian Atmosphere Model (CanAM5), which incorporates the Canadian Land Surface Scheme (CLASS) and the Canadian Terrestrial Ecosystem Model (CTEM). The ocean is represented by a CCCma-customized version of the Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean model (NEMO), with ocean biogeochemistry represented by the Canadian Model of Ocean Carbon (CMOC) in the main model version labelled as CanESM5. The atmosphere and ocean components are coupled by means of the Canadian Coupler (CanCPL).

Global-mean surface temperature changes in CanESM5 are generally consistent with the observations over the period from 1850 to 2000. However, a divergence between the model and the observations is found from 2000 to 2014, with a warming larger in the model than observed. The divergence could be due to (i) errors in the CMIP6 forcing datasets, (ii) natural internal variability, (iii) incorrect partitioning of heat across components of the climate system, or (iv) a higher climate sensitivity in the model than in the real world. Taking into account the contribution of natural internal variability in the cascade uncertainty.

DISTENDER sets the CanESM5 as a representative of the upper-level climate change sensitivity of the climate models.

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3.3 EC-Earth3

EC-Earth is a state-of-art climate model developed by research and operational meteorological services under the European consortium. The third generation of the EC-Earth (i.e., EC-Earth-3) is one of the moderately sensitive climate models of CMIP6. EC-Earth-3 has different configurations contributing to different MIPs. Its atmospheric component is ECMWF's Integrated forecast system (IFS), and the oceanic component is called the Nucleus of European Modelling of Ocean (NEMO). The horizontal resolution of T511 and T159 for IFS and 0.25deg and 1deg for NEMO are used for high and low versions of the model, respectively. Oceanic state variables and atmospheric fluxes are exchanged at the ocean and the atmosphere interface. It also includes the land surface module Hydrology Tiled ECMWF Scheme of Surface Exchanges over Land (HTESSEL). The different configuration of EC-Earth-3 consists of the representation of vegetation, atmospheric chemistry, marine biogeochemistry, and land ice. For example, the EC-Earth-3 configuration with vegetation model LPJ-GUESS (short for Lund-Potsdam-Jena General Ecosystem Simulator) is called EC-Earth-3veg (Döscher et al. 2022, Wyser et al. 2020).

EC-Earth-3 ensemble Simulations for the historical period show approximately 0.5K warm bias in the global mean of near-surface air temperature. It is reasoned to be caused by warmer oceans, primarily due to warm bias over the Southern Ocean. It makes EC-Earth-3 a warm outlier which is beneficial in risk and vulnerability analysis in the worst-case scenario (Sobolowski et al 2022). The ensemble spread is large for simulated temperature, and ensemble members show a larger bias spread over the northern hemisphere. However, the bias patterns among these members remain consistent over the southern hemisphere. Also, similar to most climate models, EC-Earth-3 shows more precipitation bias over the tropics and a double Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) pattern. Besides magnitude overestimation due to an overactive hydrological cycle (Hwang and Frierson, 2013), global precipitation patterns are represented well by the model. EC-Earth-3 efficiently simulates the mean sea level pressure and its interannual variability. The reported bias and model performance is well within the CMIP model frames.

For DISTENDER's dynamical downscaling task the EC-Earth-3veg model with control member (r1i1p1f1) is selected. Figure 5 illustrates the existing coarser observations, GCM, and CORDEX simulation and also the added information because of high-resolution (3.9km) dynamical downscaling within DISTENDER project. It will be analysed and discussed further in subsequent task 4.3 of WP4.

Figure 5. Average precipitation for June 2013 from (a) daily gridded land-only observational dataset over Europe i.e., E-OBS at 11km, (b) CMIP6 EC-Earth-3veg simulation, and its dynamical downscaling (c) at 11km using COSMO-CLM and (d) at 3.9km using ICON-CLM.

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3.4 MPI-ESM1.2-HR

The Max Planck Institute for Meteorology Earth System Model (MPI-ESM1.2) with HighResMIP protocol (MPI-ESM1.2-HR) improves the horizontal resolution of the ocean (0.4 to 0.1°) and atmosphere (T127 to T255) components, as well as reviewed the effects of substituting the Pacanowski and Philander (PP) vertical ocean mixing scheme with the K-profile parameterization (KPP). The high resolution in the ocean reduced biases in both the ocean interior and in the atmosphere (Gutjahr et al. 2019). This means that a high-resolution ocean has a major impact on the mean state of coupled ocean-atmosphere system. The T255 atmosphere reduces the surface wind stress and improves ocean mixed layer depths in both hemispheres (Gutjahr et al. 2019). The reduced wind forcing, in turn, slows the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC), reducing it to observed values. In the North Atlantic, however, the reduced surface wind causes a weakening of the subpolar gyre and thus a slowing down of the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation (AMOC), when the PP scheme is used. The KPP scheme, on the other hand, causes stronger open-ocean convection which spins up the subpolar gyres, ultimately leading to a stronger and stable AMOC, even when coupled to the T255 atmosphere, thus retaining all the positive effects of a higher-resolved atmosphere.

Most of MPI-ESM1.2-HR simulations simulate realistic sea surface temperatures, but about 1 to 2°C. The main explanation for this cold bias is a too-zonal NAC, causing a too-far-southward intrusion of fresh and cold Labrador Sea water (Müller et al., 2018) and insufficient northward heat transport by the AMOC (Wang et al., 2014). Another reason could be too much export of Mediterranean water at about 1000 m depth, thus leading to a too-strong halocline that inhibits vertical mixing. **These features make MPI-ESM1.2-HR as a good representative for the lower level in climate change sensitivity in DISTENDER.**

3.5 Sources of data

3.5.1 World Climate Research Programme

The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, of the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP), is now in its sixth phase (CMIP6). CMIP6 coordinates somewhat independent model intercomparison activities and their experiments which have adopted a common infrastructure for collecting, organizing, and distributing output from models performing common sets of experiments. The data is available through the ESGF platform (<https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/projects/cmip6/>).

The Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) Peer-to-Peer (P2P) enterprise system is a collaboration that develops, deploys and maintains software infrastructure for the management, dissemination, and analysis of model output and observational data. ESGF's primary goal is to facilitate advancements in Earth System Science. It is an interagency and international effort led by the Department of Energy (DOE), and co-funded by National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), National Science Foundation (NSF), and international laboratories such as the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M) German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ), the Australian National University (ANU) National Computational

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Infrastructure (NCI), Institute Pierre-Simon Laplace (IPSL), and the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA). The ESGF mission is to:

- Support CMIP activities and prepare for future assessments.
- Develop data and metadata facilities for inclusion of observations and reanalysis products for CMIP use.

The complete archive of CMIP6 output is made available for search and download via any one of the following portals:

- USA, PCMDI/LLNL (California) - <https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/cmip6/>
- France, IPSL - <https://esgf-node.ipsl.upmc.fr/search/cmip6-ipsl/>
- Germany, DKRZ - <https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/search/cmip6-dkrz/>
- UK, CEDA - <https://esgf-index1.ceda.ac.uk/search/cmip6-ceda/>

“We acknowledge the World Climate Research Programme, which, through its Working Group on Coupled Modelling, coordinated and promoted CMIP6. We thank the climate modeling groups for producing and making available their model output, the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) for archiving the data and providing access, and the multiple funding agencies who support CMIP6 and ESGF.”

3.5.2 Copernicus

The Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu#!/home>) has the global climate projection data from CMIP6 and regional simulations from CORDEX. The CDS is the main user interface of the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) implemented by ECMWF on behalf of the EU. The published data is a key input to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).

Climate projections come from global and regional climate models and provide information about the future evolution of the planet’s climate system at global and local scales. This quantitative information about climate change is highly relevant for developing adaptation strategies for the future and thus an important component of the catalogue of C3S datasets.

The climate projections in the CDS (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu>) are subsets of data generated under international climate model intercomparison activities, like CMIP (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project) for global projections and CORDEX (Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment) for regional projections. The CMIP and CORDEX projects design the intercomparison experiments and collect global/regional climate projection information from climate modelling centres all over the world. These datasets are archived at the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF), a federated infrastructure maintained by and primarily aimed at research institutions. C3S relies on the ESGF datasets but makes them more appropriate for climate service applications, by creating a robust and resilient system, which ensures continuous availability and includes additional quality control on the data.

The publication of CMIP6 data in the CDS is an important milestone, providing users of C3S with very new, state-of-the-art global climate projection data, which will be intensively used

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and referred to in the coming years. The main features of the dataset can be summarised as follows:

Historical simulations (validation runs for the past) and scenario simulations (future projections) are available. Simulations under a number of scenarios are available (see the CDS dataset documentation). Around 50 variables from more than 50 different Global Climate Models (GCMs) will be available. These are represented on single levels (typically surface, but also top of the atmosphere) or pressure levels (between 1,000 hPa and 1 hPa). The data are available at monthly and daily temporal resolution.

Computational processes will be on offer in this catalogue entry with subsetting options already included in the interface. This is a new feature of the CDS catalogue, which exploits processing services run at the location of the data, thus making it unnecessary for users to download large datasets. Sub-setting can be done in the vertical direction (choice of pressure levels or surface), horizontally (geographic selection), or in time (selection of the time-period required).

C3S implicitly supports the IPCC assessment through its contribution to the IPCC interactive climate atlas. This is a tool to visualise and assess different global and regional climate projections and will complement the IPCC AR6 report. C3S has provided support to upload many CORDEX simulations for regions outside Europe to ESGF, and to quality-control European and non-European climate projection data for the regions designated by CORDEX.

3.6 Data analysis

Climate projection data is modeled data from the global climate model compilations of the Coupled Model Inter-comparison Projects (CMIPs), overseen by the World Climate Research Program. Data presented is CMIP6, derived from the Sixth phase of the CMIPs. Projection data is presented at a $1.0^\circ \times 1.0^\circ$ (100km x 100km) resolution.

There are different on-line platforms that allow the analysis and visualisation of CMIP6 data. Specifically, the following tools have been used to prepare this document and to analyse the data to be used in the downscaling:

- **Climate Change Knowledge Portal**
(<https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/>)
The Climate Change Knowledge Portal (CCKP) provides global data on historical and future climate, vulnerabilities, and impacts. Explore them via Country and Watershed views. Access synthesized Country Profiles to gain deeper insights into climate risks and adaptation actions. The Climate Change Knowledge Portal (CCKP) is the hub for climate-related information, data, and tools for the World Bank Group (WBG).
- **Global climate and weather data (WorldClim)**
(<https://www.worldclim.org/data/cmip6/cmip6climate.html#>)
WorldClim is a database of high spatial resolution global weather and climate data. These data can be used for mapping and spatial modeling.
- **Canadian Climate Data and Scenarios (CCDS)**

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Figure 6. Maps of the CMIP6 multi-model ensemble mean temperature (°C) for the period 2040-2059 for the scenarios SSP126, SSP245, SSP370 and SSP585.

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Figure 7. Monthly time series (European domain spatial average) of the CMIP6 multi-model ensemble mean temperature (°C) for the period 2040-2059 for the scenarios SSP126, SSP245, SSP370 and SSP585 and historical reference period (1995-2012).

In the Figure 7 we can see the mean monthly temperature for the same period, for each of the scenarios and the mean reference temperature in the period 1995-2014. Especially in the summer months (June, July, and August) significant increases (of up to 5 degrees) in temperature are expected according to the prediction of some models for the SSP5-85 scenario. If we look at the model ensemble, the increases would be between 2° and 3°, with the SSP5-8.5 scenario with a slightly higher increase.

Figure 8 shows the projected change in precipitation for the period 2040-2059 with respect to the 1995-2014 reference period based on the ensemble of CMIP6 models for the four scenarios selected in DISTENDER.

Figure 8. Maps of the CMIP6 multi-model ensemble precipitation percent (%) change anomaly for the period 2040-2059 for the scenarios SSP126, SSP245, SSP370 and SSP585.

It can be clearly seen that a significant reduction in precipitation is expected in southern Europe, the greater the reduction as radiative forcing increases. The reduction in precipitation would be up to 40% in the SSP585 scenario in southern Europe.

The Figure 9 analyses the same information as the previous figure but now by spatially averaging the domain and showing the expected precipitation change in a monthly time series. In the summer months there will be a significant reduction in precipitation, especially in the SPP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios. Slight increases may occur in the winter months. The figure also shows a large dispersion of results between the different CMIP6 models, which is why the coloured areas have a large width, while for temperature this dispersion of results was much smaller. For example, in the summer months some models project sharp decreases in precipitation and others project a slight increase in precipitation for the same month and scenario. This is where the uncertainty of the scenarios and simulations comes into play, which is why it is convenient to use information from several models, as will be done in DISTENDER.

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Projected precipitation percent change anomaly for 2040-2059 (Ref. period 1995-2014). Multi-Model Ensemble. Data source:CMIP6. Graphics tool: CCKP

Figure 9. Monthly time series (European domain spatial average) of the CMIP6 multi-model ensemble precipitation percent (%) change anomaly for the period 2040-2059 for the scenarios SSP126, SSP245, SSP370 and SSP585 and historical reference period (1995-2012).

The temporal evolution every 10 years of the expected changes in temperature (°C) and precipitation (mm) with respect to the 1981-2000 reference period is shown below. The data analyzed correspond to the results of the simulations of the three climate models selected in DISTENDER: CanESM5 (Can), EC-Earth3 (Earth) and MPI-ESM1-2-HR (MPI). It has been performed at country level, including the 4 countries containing case studies in DISTENDER: Spain (Dehesa-Montado case study) see Figure 10, Portugal (Guimaraes and Dehesa-Montado case studies) see Figure 11, Italy (Torino Metropolitan case study) see Figure 12, Austria see Figure 13 and The Netherlands (North-East case study) see Figure 14.

Figure 10. Decadal time series for Spain (Dehesa and Montados CS) of the CMIP6 CanESM5, EC-EARTH3 and MPI-ESM1-2-HR global climate models for the change of the (top) temperature (°C) and (bottom) precipitation (mm) respect to the reference period 1981-2000 for the scenarios SSP126, SSP245, SSP370 and SSP585.

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Figure 11. Decadal time series for Portugal (Guimaraes and Dehesa and Montados CSs) of the CMIP6 CanESM5, EC-EARTH3 and MPI-ESM1-2-HR global climate models for the change of the (top) temperature (°C) and (bottom) precipitation (mm) respect to the reference period 1981-2000 for the scenarios SSP126, SSP245, SSP370 and SSP585.

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Figure 12. Decadal time series for Italy (Torino CS) of the CMIP6 CanESM5, EC-EARTH3 and MPI-ESM1-2-HR global climate models for the change of the (top) temperature (°C) and (bottom) precipitation (mm) respect to the reference period 1981-2000 for the scenarios SSP126, SSP245, SSP370 and SSP585.

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Figure 13. Decadal time series for Austria (Austria CS) of the CMIP6 CanESM5, EC-EARTH3 and MPI-ESM1-2-HR global climate models for the change of the (top) temperature (°C) and (bottom) precipitation (mm) respect to the reference period 1981-2000 for the scenarios SSP126, SSP245, SSP370 and SSP585.

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Figure 14. Decadal time series for The Netherlands (North-East The Netherlands CS) of the CMIP6 CanESM5, EC-EARTH3 and MPI-ESM1-2-HR global climate models for the change of the (top) temperature (°C) and (bottom) precipitation (mm) respect to the reference period 1981-2000 for the scenarios SSP126, SSP245, SSP370 and SSP585.

The projected model results for temperatures in the five countries follow very similar patterns. A gradual increase in temperatures is expected. In the year 2050, an increase of one degree is expected according to the SSP126 scenario, up to four degrees for the SSP585 scenario. The three models show a change in trend starting in 2040 in the SSP126 scenario (blue line), which is the scenario where a greater reduction in GHG emissions is expected, such that the temperature in 2050 would be lower than in 2040, while the other scenarios show a general increase in all decades.

In the temperature graphs it is clear that the model that produces a higher increase is Earth, the one that produces a lower increase is MPI, and in between them is Can. The difference between Earth and MPI can be as much as two degrees. This justifies the selection of these three models in the project, since it allows to have a representative range of results and to be able to analyze the uncertainty of the results.

As for precipitation, there is not as clear a trend as for temperature; the expected increases and decreases depend a lot on the model. For the precipitation variable, there is a greater influence of the model used than of the scenario analyzed. The Can model tends to project a slight increase in precipitation in all scenarios except SSP370. The Earth model projects slight changes in precipitation and the MPI model projects decreases in precipitation in all scenarios. In the southern European countries (Spain, Portugal, and Italy) we can conclude that a reduction in precipitation between 50 and 100 mm is expected, and in the countries of Austria and the Netherlands increases of up to 200 mm are expected. But as mentioned above, there is not such a clear trend decade after decade.

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Conclusions

To understand the evolution of the climate in the coming decades, we have global climate models (GCMs) as tools for simulating the interactions between the earth-ocean-atmosphere system using the fundamental thermodynamic equations. These models perform their simulations based on scenarios where the concentrations of GHGs are changing. The scenarios are a combination of socioeconomic pathways and climate forcing radiation. In DISTENDER 'Tier 1' CMIP6 scenarios are the selected scenarios: SSP126, SSP245, SSP370, SSP585. The timing and magnitude of projected future climate change is uncertain due to the ambiguity introduced by human choices, natural variability, and scientific uncertainty which includes uncertainty in both scientific modeling and climate sensitivity.

The role of climate scenarios in adaptation assessment and planning ranges from irrelevant to highly relevant depending on the approach, which is determined by nature of the case, scale of the area, climate data availability and capacity to handle them, and time scale. If climate scenarios are available and reliable (i.e., they depict plausible future climate), they are beneficial for picturing future climate and understanding its impacts. They are also useful, and probably more important, for testing the robustness of adaptation response or policies, despite their uncertainties. GCMs are considered the best in depicting future climate driven by anthropogenic forcing, but they are too coarse for many impact studies. Treatments of the coarse scale GCM outputs before being used as inputs to many impact assessments and studies, in particular downscaling methods: statistical and dynamical. Considering the different level of climate sensitivity to the radiative forcing data and the contribution of natural internal variability to the cascade uncertainty,

DISTENDER selected the CanESM5, EC-EARTH, and MPI-ESM1 as representatives of the upper-, medium- and lower-level climate sensitivity of the CMIP6 Global Climate Models. After an analysis of climate change related data with a global resolution we can conclude that it is difficult to implement adaptation and mitigation measures on a local scale with such information. A corresponding downscaling procedure is necessary in order to have more detailed information in each case study.

Until 2050, a gradual increase in temperature is expected in all scenarios except in the SSP126 scenario where the upward trend in temperature changes from 2040 onwards. Annual precipitation is projected to decrease in southern Europe and increase in the rest of the countries.

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